

Analysis of Clarke vector hodograph shape for diagnostics of inter-turn fault in stators of induction electric motors

Jacek Wodecki, Anna Michalak, Justyna Hebda-Sobkowicz, Radosław Zimroz, Agnieszka Wyłomańska, Marcin Wolkiewicz, Krzysztof Szabat, Sebastien Weisse, and Jerome Valire

Abstract—In this paper, a novel approach is presented for assessing the quantity of compromised stator windings utilizing the Clarke vector hodograph (later referred to as "hodograph"). The fault is understood in the context of inter-turn short-circuits of stator windings in an induction motor. Experimental investigation on a dedicated test rig reveals that with undamaged windings, the hodograph manifests itself as a circle; otherwise, it assumes an elliptical form. The angle of inclination of the ellipse, as well as the degree of flattening, indicates the presence of the fault that can be quantified. To detect faults related to stator defects, an algorithm is proposed that allows for parameterizing the features and investigating their monotonicity. Furthermore, an analysis of feature distribution per fault case is performed. These investigations led to the construction of a statistical model in two-dimensional feature space that allows for performing model-based diagnostics and the quantification of the severity of the fault.

Index Terms—fault diagnostic, hodograph analysis, induction motor, inter-turn short-circuits, statistical analysis, feature extraction

I. INTRODUCTION

Squirrel-cage induction motors are the most common type used in industrial drive systems. This is due to their simple design, high durability, low production costs, and high adjustability. More than 32% of all the faults are inter-turn short-circuits [1]. In a quarter of faulty machines, the stator core was faulty. Tests show that as the power rating of the

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Jacek Wodecki, Anna Michalak, Justyna Hebda-Sobkowicz and Radosław Zimroz are with the Faculty of Geoengineering, Mining and Geology, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Wrocław 50-421, Poland (e-mail: {jacek.wodecki, anna.michalak, justyna.hebda-sobkowicz, radoslaw.zimroz}@pwr.edu.pl)

Agnieszka Wyłomańska is with the Faculty of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Wrocław 50-376, Poland (e-mail: agnieszka.wylomanska@pwr.edu.pl)

Marcin Wolkiewicz, Marcin Pawlak and Krzysztof Szabat are with the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, 50-370 Wrocław, Poland (e-mail: {marcin.wolkiewicz, marcin.pawlak, krzysztof.szabat}@pwr.edu.pl)

Sebastien Weisse and Jerome Valire are with the SAFRAN Electrical & Power, Toulouse, France.

motors increases, the role of mechanical damage decreases in favour of electrical damage. As shown in [1] 84% of the electrical faults occurred in the stator. It usually results from a single-turn short-circuit, which is difficult to detect and can cause complete winding failure. For this reason, early detection of this type of damage is crucial [2], [3].

Numerous methods for diagnosing stator winding faults in induction motors have been developed [4], [5]. They rely on signals such as stator phase current [6], temperature [7], active and reactive power [8], vibrations [9], and axial flux [10], but also FEM modeling [11]. One of the most fundamental yet highly effective methods is the spectral analysis of the signal using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) [5]. This approach forms the basis for Motor Current Signature Analysis (MCSA) [6], [12], which enables the determination of the degree of motor damage by analyzing the amplitude of harmonics at frequencies characteristic of the damage. While spectral analysis is computationally efficient and widely used, it has limitations, particularly in dynamic operating conditions. Unfortunately, FFT-based methods require a relatively long measurement time to achieve any usable resolution of the spectrum [13]. Furthermore, varying load and speed conditions can negatively impact the accuracy of MCSA due to spectral smearing [14].

To address these challenges, time-frequency analysis techniques such as the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) [15] and the Hilbert-Huang Transform (HHT) [16] have been developed. They can be very effective for non-linear and non-stationary signals; however, both methods require significant computational resources and may struggle with real-time applications due to their complexity and processing time.

In addition to the previously mentioned techniques, state estimation approaches based on Kalman filtering have emerged as powerful tools for early detection of inter-turn short-circuit faults in induction motors. The Extended Kalman Filter (EKF), in particular, has demonstrated significant advantages due to its ability to handle the nonlinear system dynamics and measurement noise inherent in motor operation. Merraoui and Ferdjouni [17] proposed two variants of EKF for fault detection and isolation of inter-turn short circuits in induction motors, where fault factors (defined as the ratio of healthy turns to the total number of turns) are estimated to detect and localize stator winding faults. The approach provides a quantitative assessment of fault severity while minimizing

false alarms. Similarly, Ghanbari et al. [18] developed a Kalman filter-based technique that processes lower sideband frequencies for stator turn-fault detection in induction motors, achieving higher accuracy even with a minimal number of shorted turns. More recently, Mehmood et al. [19] presented a robust algorithm utilizing Kalman filtering to extract motor current signatures and motor voltage signatures, demonstrating exceptional performance in discriminating between actual inter-turn faults and non-fault conditions such as voltage quality problems and heavy load changes.

An alternative approach is the analysis of the spatial vector module of the stator current using EPVA (Extended Park's Vector Approach) [6], [20], [21]. EPVA focuses on observing the shape and position of the resulting Clarke vector hodograph, derived from the spatial vector components of the stator current. Considering the specific requirements regarding the application of the presented methodology, hodograph analysis offers a significant advantage over traditional methods such as FFT, STFT, or HHT. Unlike spectral methods, hodograph analysis enables rapid evaluation based on even a single period of the current signal. This makes it particularly useful in real-world real-time industrial applications, where rapid fault detection is critical. Additionally, hodograph analysis does not rely on frequency domain transformations, allowing it to operate effectively without extensive signal preprocessing.

The Clarke Transform ($\alpha - \beta$ transformation) and Park's Transform (d-q transformation) are both used in the analysis and control of three-phase systems, such as electric motors. Each has its advantages, and the choice between them depends on the specific application, but the Clarke transform does not require information about shaft position. Clarke Transform converts three-phase quantities (a, b, c) into a two-axis stationary reference frame (α, β). The $\alpha - \beta$ components provide a clear representation of asymmetries or imbalances in the system, making it easier to detect issues like stator winding faults or voltage unbalance.

The hodograph is a graphical, mathematical tool used to analyze the trajectories of vectors in a coordinate system. In our work, the hodograph is applied to analyse current signals in motors powered by voltage source inverters (VSI). In contrast to FFT-based methods, our approach utilizes the hodograph to visualize current trajectories in real-time, enabling faster and more accurate identification of distortions. Compared to existing diagnostic methods, our solution offers higher fault detection accuracy, lower computational requirements, and real-time applicability for the automatic classification of stator winding faults.

In this article, the authors present a methodology for assessing the damage of a stator winding, defined as a short circuit between consecutive coils of a winding of a given phase. The described method presents two variants. The first variant assumes the parameterization of hodographs based directly on empirical data. In the second approach, the theoretical ellipses are fitted to the empirical hodograms, and the parameters of those ellipses are analyzed. The proposed algorithm has several advantages. Firstly, it is fully automatic and does not require any

contextual knowledge to construct the classification model, assuming sufficient training data is available. Secondly, it is based on standard, well-established methods (i.e., Clarke transform, Principal Component Analysis, Maximum Likelihood Estimation, Gaussian Mixture Model, etc.). Finally, after the model is constructed, its evaluation on new data is simple and time-efficient. Moreover, the novelty lies in the quantification of the spatial vector hodograph parameters and assessment of the health state. The fact of modeling the feature space using a Gaussian Mixture Model, which provides a high degree of separability of particular fault classes, while allowing for rapid evaluation of the incoming data samples.

The article is structured as follows: section II describes the experimental conditions, test rig and obtained data, section III lays out the methodology proposed for data analysis, section IV presents the results with the distinction of two proposed variants of the method, section V provides a discussion regarding further optimization of the obtained results, and finally section VI states the conclusions.

II. EXPERIMENT AND DATA DESCRIPTION

Experimental tests were carried out on a specially prepared laboratory bench consisting of a test induction motor with a rated power of 1.5 kW and a DC motor that provided the load torque. The test rig scheme is shown in Fig. 1, while Fig. 2 presents its actual view. The rated parameters of the motor tested are grouped in Table I. The construction of the motor used allowed for the physical modeling of inter-turn short-circuits in each of the three phases in a range of 0–10 stator turns.

Fig. 1: Scheme of the test rig

Fig. 2: Real view of experimental setup

Fig. 3: Terminal board of prepared induction motor.

The motor tested was fed from a frequency converter in the range $f_s = 10 - 50$ Hz, operating in an open loop under scalar control $\frac{U_s}{f_s} = const$. The switching frequency of the inverter was set to 10 kHz. The stator phase currents were measured using LEM LA 25-NP transducers and acquired using a National Instruments DAQ card (model NI-PXIE 4492). The data were processed and analyzed in a custom application developed in LabVIEW 2023. The stator winding has been specially prepared so that it is possible to short-circuit the correct number of turns in each phase of the stator, where 0 indicates no short circuits (no fault) and values 1-10 indicate the number of short-circuited windings. A corresponding group of coils was led to the terminal board, and the short-circuit was physically modeled through a connection between the terminals with the N_{sh} parameter indicating the number of shorted coils for a given scenario (Fig. 3). During the measurements, the short-circuit loop included resistances of 1, 2, 3, 5, and 10 turns, respectively, as well as the short-circuit resistance, which also includes contact resistance.

TABLE I: Rated parameters of the tested induction motor.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Power	P_N	1500	[W]
Torque	T_N	10.16	[Nm]
Speed	n_N	1410	[RPM]
Stator phase voltage	U_{sN}	230	[V]
Stator current	I_{sN}	3.7	[A]
Frequency	f_{sN}	50	[Hz]
Pole pairs number	p_p	2	[-]
Number of rotor bars	N_{rb}	26	[-]
Number of stator winding loops	N_{st}	312	[-]

Fig. 4: Comparison of measured currents in the stator winding and the shorted circuit.

To confirm the occurrence of very high currents during a short circuit, measurements of the stator currents were conducted. The results are presented in Fig. 4, which shows the stator phase current under nominal operating conditions (I_{sA}), with an RMS value of 3.7 A, as well as the short-circuit current waveforms for two scenarios: a short circuit in

1 turn and a short circuit in 5 turns. In the case of a short circuit in 1 turn (I_{sh1}), the RMS value of the short-circuit current reaches 16.3 A, demonstrating a significant increase compared to normal operating conditions. For a short circuit in 5 turns (I_{sh5}), the RMS value further increases to 23.3 A, confirming that the short-circuit current grows with the number of shorted turns. These measurements clearly illustrate that, during a short circuit, very high currents flow, which can have a destructive effect on the stator windings. The rapid temperature rise in the short-circuit area may lead to complete destruction of the windings, highlighting the need for rapid detection and elimination of such faults.

III. METHODOLOGY

Overall methodology presented in this article consists of consecutive data processing steps occurring as follows:

- 1) Signal segmentation into individual periods of the main sine wave of current signals,
- 2) Signal denoising,
- 3) Spatial vector (Clarke vector) calculation,
- 4) Calculation of Shape Coefficient (SC) and orientation angle using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), or ellipse fitting,
- 5) Statistical analysis of SC and angle distribution for varying levels of winding fault,
- 6) Modeling of SC-angle feature space using Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM).

The method is based on the analysis of hodographs based on individual cycles of the current signal, which translates to individual loops of the hodograph. The number of segments obtained from a measurement allowed to perform statistical analysis of the results based on empirical distributions of calculated parameters. Hence, the subsequent subsections III-A to III-E (Denoising, Clarke vector calculation, hodograph analysis by PCA or by ellipse fitting) are described for a single period of signal (a single hodograph loop). Then subsections III-F to III-G (distribution estimation and statistical modeling) are performed on the whole set of calculated features. GMM enables the construction of a theoretical model of a given data distribution, namely the probability that a point belongs to a given class. Consequently, for a new observation, it is possible to determine to which state it belongs based on the model obtained.

A. Denoising

In order to be able to clearly observe the shape of an individual hodograph, the current signals require denoising. The goal of this step is to remove the high-frequency oscillations describing the inverter switching. This operation is performed using local regression using weighted linear least squares and a second-degree polynomial model [22]. The regression is performed locally within a window of a given span. In this implementation, the regression weights for each point in the window are given by the tricube function:

$$w_i = \left(1 - \left|\frac{x - x_i}{d(x)}\right|^3\right)^3 \quad (1)$$

where x is the predictor value associated with the response value to be smoothed, x_i are the nearest neighbors of x as defined by the span, and $d(x)$ is the distance along the abscissa from x to the most distant predictor value within the span. The tricube function is used because, among other weighting functions that decrease to zero at the extremes, it enhances the distributional approximation of an estimate of the error variance. It has been established that this function should provide adequate smoothing in almost all situations, especially with outliers [22].

B. Spatial vector calculation and hodograph

Spatial vector transformation (also known as Clarke transformation or $\alpha - \beta$ transformation) allows to perform the transition from three-phase ABC coordinates describing current signals to a two-dimensional $\alpha\beta$ representation called spatial vector [23]. This representation allows to visualize and further analysis of the hodograph ellipse. Spatial vector components are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{cases} I_\alpha = \frac{2}{3} (I_A - \frac{1}{2}(I_B + I_C)) \\ I_\beta = \frac{2}{3} (\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}(I_B - I_C)) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Based on those components, one can construct a hodograph, which for an induction motor in the ideal state takes the shape of a circle. However, when various types of faults occur, the shape becomes an ellipse with a given orientation angle Θ and degree of flattening SC, which is a divergence from the perfect circle, that can be an indicator of the severity of the fault (see Fig. 5a) [24], [25]. SC is calculated from orthogonal dimensions of the hodograph $D = \{d_1, d_2\}$ - length and width.

Fig. 5: Hodograph features (a) and general idea of PCA (b)

C. Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis posits that a dataset with N observations across K variables can be conceptualized as a point cloud in K -dimensional space [26]. The aim of PCA is to rotate the local coordinate system to maximize variance along new dimensions, ensuring the first dimension captures the greatest variance, followed by subsequent dimensions (see Fig. 5b). This transformation yields new data values across these dimensions, termed principal components. The resultant feature space predominantly encapsulates the original dataset within the initial principal components, which retain the majority of its information. Given the high information content of these primary components, PCA serves as a method for reducing dimensionality in various analyses.

Given n observations of m -dimensional data stacked into a matrix $X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$, the principal components can be calculated using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD):

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{n-1}} \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^T, \quad (3)$$

where $U \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $V \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ are unitary matrices and $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ contains the nonnegative real *singular values* of non-increasing magnitude ($\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_m \geq 0$). Principal components are the orthonormal column vectors of the matrix \mathbf{V} , and the variance of the i -th component is equal to σ_i^2 .

D. Ellipse fitting using least-squares criterion

The conic representation of the ellipse can be defined as follows:

$$aI_\alpha^2 + bI_\alpha I_\beta + cI_\beta^2 + dI_\alpha + eI_\beta + f = 0, \quad (4)$$

where $M = [I_\alpha, I_\beta]$ is the set of points in the Cartesian plane, a, b, c, d, e, f are the parameters to be estimated, and $b^2 - 4ac < 0$. The Eq. 4 can also be expressed in the vector form as:

$$\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{I} = 0, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{I} = [I_\alpha^2, I_\alpha I_\beta, I_\beta^2, I_\alpha, I_\beta, 1]$ is the vector of coordinates of the points on the conic equation and $\mathbf{v} = [a, b, c, d, e, f]$ is the vector of parameters. By minimizing the sum of the squared distances of the curve to the given points, the problem of fitting a conic section can be solved. Using the substitution of I_α with $I_\alpha \cos(\hat{\Theta}) + I_\beta \sin(\hat{\Theta})$ and I_β with $-I_\alpha \sin(\hat{\Theta}) + I_\beta \cos(\hat{\Theta})$ and simplifying it, the orientation can easily be found and reduced. Thus, the angle is calculated from the vector of estimated parameters $\hat{\mathbf{v}} = [\hat{a}, \hat{b}, \hat{c}, \hat{d}, \hat{e}, \hat{f}]$:

$$\hat{\Theta} = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\hat{b}}{\hat{c} - \hat{a}} \right). \quad (6)$$

In the next step, it is required to perform the calculations that lead to obtaining the geometric description of the ellipse in the form of SC. Using the $\hat{\Theta}$ angle, the other constants were determined using the following formulas:

$$\begin{cases} \tilde{a} = \hat{a} * \cos(\hat{\Theta})^2 - \hat{b} * \cos(\hat{\Theta}) * \sin(\hat{\Theta}) + \hat{c} * \sin(\hat{\Theta})^2 \\ \tilde{c} = \hat{a} * \sin(\hat{\Theta})^2 + \hat{b} * \cos(\hat{\Theta}) * \sin(\hat{\Theta}) + \hat{c} * \cos(\hat{\Theta})^2 \\ \tilde{d} = \hat{d} * \cos(\hat{\Theta}) - \hat{e} * \sin(\hat{\Theta}) \\ \tilde{e} = \hat{d} * \sin(\hat{\Theta}) - \hat{e} * \cos(\hat{\Theta}). \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Next, the representation of the non-tilted ellipse allows one to use a square completion method to obtain the following:

$$F = 1 + \frac{\tilde{d}^2}{4\tilde{a}} + \frac{\tilde{e}^2}{4\tilde{c}}. \quad (8)$$

Then, the dimensions of the ellipse expressed by the lengths of the longer and shorter axes are calculated as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{d}}^{fit} = \{\hat{d}_1^{fit}, \hat{d}_2^{fit}\} = \{\sqrt{F/\tilde{a}}, \sqrt{F/\tilde{c}}\}. \quad (9)$$

Finally, SC is calculated as a ratio of the shorter axis to the longer axis:

$$\hat{SC} = \frac{\min(\hat{\mathbf{d}}^{fit})}{\max(\hat{\mathbf{d}}^{fit})}. \quad (10)$$

E. Hodograph features estimation using PCA

The geometric features of the hodograph can be obtained using PCA calculated on the two-column matrix $M = [I_\alpha, I_\beta]$ [26]. The geometric features are obtained based on eigenvalues and eigenvectors calculated as part of the PCA algorithm. In particular, the angle is calculated from the first eigenvector $\hat{v}_1 = \{\hat{v}_1(1), \hat{v}_1(2)\}$, such as:

$$\hat{\Theta} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\hat{v}_1(2)}{\hat{v}_1(1)} \right). \quad (11)$$

Similarly, dimensions can be calculated from eigenvalues $\hat{E} = \{\hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2\}$, such as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{d}}^{PCA} = \begin{cases} \hat{d}_1^{PCA} = 2\sqrt{(\hat{e}_1)} \\ \hat{d}_2^{PCA} = 2\sqrt{(\hat{e}_2)}. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Hence, the shape coefficient SC of the hodograph ellipse can be defined as:

$$\hat{SC} = \frac{\hat{d}_1^{PCA}}{\hat{d}_2^{PCA}}. \quad (13)$$

F. Empirical density estimation

Empirical distribution density is calculated using the kernel density estimator, which is the estimated empirical probability density function [27], [28]. For real values of the vector x , the estimated empirical distribution is calculated as follows:

$$\hat{f}_h(x) = \frac{1}{nh} \sum_{i=1}^n K \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h} \right), \quad (14)$$

where x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n are samples of the data, $\mathbf{K}(\cdot)$ is the kernel smoothing function, n is the sample size, and h is the bandwidth. In this implementation, a Gaussian kernel is used.

The bandwidth value is obtained using the so-called *Silverman's rule of thumb* [28]. For the assumption of a Gaussian kernel, the optimal choice for h (that minimizes the mean integrated squared error) is:

$$h = \left(\frac{4\hat{\sigma}^5}{3n} \right)^{\frac{1}{5}} \approx 1.06\hat{\sigma}n^{-1/5}, \quad (15)$$

where $\hat{\sigma}$ is the estimator of the standard deviation of the samples and n is the number of samples.

G. Gaussian mixture model estimation

Gaussian Mixture Model is estimated using Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm, which is an iterative optimization method for estimation of unknown parameters $\Omega = \{\mu, \Sigma, \alpha\}$, given measurement data $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ in the presence of missing data [29]–[32]. EM is particularly useful for separating mixtures of Gaussian distributions (or any other) over the considered feature space. It consists of two main steps: Expectation (E-step) and Maximization (M-step), which are iterated until convergence.

In the first iteration algorithm has to be provided with some initial values of parameters Ω . It can be done by picking random means, covariances, and distribution weights, but it is a good practice to pre-estimate means $\bar{\mu}_l$, where $l \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ and K is the number of expected clusters. It can be done using some simpler (but not very useful for this problem in general) algorithm like k-means or hierarchical clustering. Then one can compute covariance matrices Σ_l based on the results of this pre-clustering, and set weights α_l to the normalized amount of points in each cluster.

1) *E-step*: This step is responsible for the estimation of the probability of belonging each data point \bar{x}_i to each cluster Ω_l :

$$p(\Omega_l | \bar{x}_i) = \alpha_l \cdot \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{d/2} |\Sigma_l|^{1/2}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\bar{x}_i - \bar{\mu}_l)^T \Sigma_l^{-1} (\bar{x}_i - \bar{\mu}_l)}, \quad (16)$$

where $l = 1, \dots, K; i = 1, \dots, N$ and N is the number of data points.

2) *M-step*: In this step, the algorithm estimates the new parameters Ω of the probability distribution of each cluster for the next iteration $t + 1$. First, the mean for each cluster is computed by calculating the mean of all points as a function of the degree of relevance of each point:

$$\mu_l^{(t+1)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N p(\Omega_l | \bar{x}_i) \bar{x}_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N p(\Omega_l | \bar{x}_i)}, \quad l = 1, \dots, K \quad (17)$$

Then, covariance matrices can be computed based on the conditional probability of the cluster occurrence:

$$\Sigma_l^{(t+1)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N p(\Omega_l | \bar{x}_i) (\bar{x}_i - \bar{\mu}_l(t))^T (\bar{x}_i - \bar{\mu}_l(t))}{\sum_{i=1}^N p(\Omega_l | \bar{x}_i)}. \quad (18)$$

At the end of the M-step, the probability of occurrence of each class is computed through the mean of probabilities of each point from the cluster as a function of the relevance degree:

$$\alpha_l^{(t+1)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N p(\Omega_l | \bar{x}_i), \quad l = 1, \dots, K \quad (19)$$

IV. RESULTS

The described methodology has been applied to the data measured on the described test rig (see Section II). For each fault scenario, the 10-second signals sampled at 51,2 kHz have been segmented into individual periods, which resulted in 500 non-overlapping windows, with a length of 1024 samples (0.02 s). An example of such signals (before and after denoising)

within a single window is presented in Fig. 6, in this case for the most severe fault scenario. Each of such data portions was denoised, converted into a spatial vector, and produced a hodograph ellipse.

Fig. 6: Current signals, raw (thin pale lines) and denoised (bold solid lines)

Fig. 7: Hodographs of the progressing stage of fault.

A comparison of exemplary ellipses for each fault level is presented in Fig. 7, where it can be observed how the angle and shape progressively change.

For each fault level (as well as for the healthy scenario), 500 hodographs were obtained. Based on each ellipse, Θ and SC were calculated using PCA (see Fig. 8 top panels) and ellipse fitting (see Fig. 8 bottom panels). The difference between the ellipse fitting approach and the PCA approach lies in the method of obtaining the parameters of hodographs. Hence, the subsequent steps are the same. First, the general behavior of the progression of the features is presented using boxplots for each fault level, including the healthy case (see Fig. 9).

Secondly, their empirical probability density functions are estimated for each fault level (see Fig. 10). It is important to understand that for the fault cases approaching healthy state (i.e., fault levels 0,1,2) the flattening of hodographs is minimal, and their shape is very close to a perfect circle. Hence, the estimated ellipse angle can suffer from lower precision of estimation, hence wider distributions.

There are several observations to be made while comparing Figures 9 and 8. The general characteristics are strictly monotonic, and their behavior is as expected. It could be argued that for the shape coefficient, the difference in values

Fig. 8: Coefficients calculated for each hodogram (10 seconds = 500 samples per fault case). Fault case order: healthy, level 1, level 2, level 3, level 5, level 10. Top panels: PCA variant, bottom panels: ellipse fitting variant.

Fig. 9: Boxplots of parameter values for phase with faulty winding. Top panels: PCA variant, bottom panels: ellipse fitting variant.

between the healthy case and the first two fault cases is small, which could make those states difficult to differentiate. It should be emphasized, however, that short-circuiting of 1-2 turns of a single phase is an early stage of the defect, which results in small quantitative changes in the amplitudes of diagnostic signals. Therefore, diagnostics at this stage of the defect is complicated, and in the case of the analysis of only the RMS value of phase currents, it is practically impossible. However, a comparison of distributions (Fig. 10) shows that there is almost no overlap between those states, but nevertheless, the non-zero overlap is still present. Another

Fig. 10: Distribution density estimates for SC and angle divided by fault severity level. Dashed lines: PCA, continuous lines: ellipse fitting.

observation is that diagnostics based on angle information alone cannot be performed because the overlap between distributions is too great.

Fig. 11: Training data used for creating GMM: PCA (upper panel) and ellipse fitting (lower panel)

To address the problem of separability, the data from all six cases for both variants have been used to estimate a two-dimensional GMM in $\{SC, \Theta\}$ feature space. Data for each fault scenario has been divided into a training set (95% - 475 samples) and a testing set (5% - 25 samples). For the training set (see Fig. 11), the model has been estimated (see Fig. 12). This representation produces classes that are clearly separable in a two-dimensional feature space. The modes of the model are defined as separate distributions. Hence, the model allows one to assign the data into particular classes, so that the newly arrived portions of the data can be labeled accordingly. Therefore, in the next step, the test set has been

evaluated using the model obtained based on training data (see Fig. 13).

Fig. 12: GMM of the feature space: PCA (upper panel) and ellipse fitting (lower panel)

Fig. 13: Test data classified using GMM. Black contours indicate the placement and orientation of the modes of the GMM. PCA (upper panel) and ellipse fitting (lower panel)

V. QUALITY OPTIMIZATION STUDY

Results presented so far describe the fundamental implementation of the proposed method. It assumes that a practical monitoring system imposes a limitation on the length of a signal sample being registered for the purpose of making

an online diagnosis. Hence, the authors present the approach that utilizes the smallest possible amount of data - a single cycle of a sine wave. However, if a particular implementation of the monitoring system allows for it, using more than one cycle per hodograph assessment yields significant benefits in robustness and class separability.

Another aspect that could be optimized is the sampling frequency itself. In the presented results, the authors use the full sampling frequency used in the measurements - 51.2 kHz, which translates into 1024 samples per cycle. However, this value can be easily reduced by a significant factor.

Fig. 14 presents results of applying each of the two abovementioned aspects of optimization to the original configuration (panel a). Panel b) presents the same analysis performed for a 32 times lower sampling frequency ($f_s = 1.6$ kHz), which translates into 32 samples per cycle. The dispersion of the point clouds representing individual fault classes is slightly increased, especially for lower faults and healthy condition, but the obtained GMM model still achieves 100% accuracy of classification, because the classes are still fully separable. This does not directly improve the quality of the obtained results, but allows to configure the real-life monitoring system at a lower sampling frequency, which lowers the data rate. This is a desirable effect for the practical implementations of the industrial monitoring systems.

Panel c) presents the second aspect of quality optimization - using four sine cycles instead of one to construct and evaluate a single hodograph. One can observe a dramatic decrease in the dispersion of point clouds, which helps to improve class separability. For the single-cycle results, the separability was acceptable, and the classification of the test data was 100% successful, but the results were achieved using data measured in laboratory conditions. One can imagine that for a real-life industrial application, the signals can be much more chaotic, and point clouds can display much greater dispersion. Hence, the authors argue that this improvement can be highly beneficial in real-life industrial scenarios.

Panel d) combines those two approaches. Hodographs are evaluated using four sine cycles measured with $f_s = 1.6$ kHz. Point cloud dispersion is significantly reduced in comparison to panel b), and is similar to the result presented in panel c). While the result in panel c) is theoretically the best, the result in panel d) presents a similar level of point cloud dispersion, but also offers significantly reduced sampling frequency, and for this reason, this configuration could be considered the optimal one. Of course, the particular user (the integrator of the monitoring system) is encouraged to adjust the particular values of those two parameters (sampling frequency, number of cycles) to their specific application, taking into consideration the sampling rate capabilities of the system and need for data rate reduction (considerations for sampling frequency adjustment) as well as the speed of the real-time response (consideration for the number of cycles).

The article successfully demonstrates that even early-stage faults (short-circuiting 1-2 turns) can be detected with high accuracy using their proposed method, despite minimal quantitative changes in amplitude-based diagnostic signals. This capability addresses known limitations in

Fig. 14: Training data used for creating GMM - Ellipse fitting variant. a) Original configuration - $f_s = 51.2$ kHz, one cycle; b) $f_s = 1.6$ kHz, one cycle; c) $f_s = 51.2$ kHz, 4 cycles; d) $f_s = 1.6$ kHz, 4 cycles.

existing methods (FFT-based MCSA, Extended Park's Vector Approach (EPVA), Neural Network-based methods), which struggle with early-stage detection and present their own disadvantages.

- FFT-based MCSA requires significant sampling frequencies and longer signals to achieve proper representation of the Fourier spectrum. Hence, this method is susceptible to load variations and non-stationary conditions, and additionally does not allow for reducing the data rate per evaluation (neither sampling frequency nor signal length).
- EPVA also needs higher sampling rates and longer data recording, with preprocessing steps such as normalization and scaling required due to sensitivity to motor specifications and load conditions. Additionally, Clarke transformation is simpler and requires fewer calculations compared to Park's Transform, which involves rotating the reference frame to align with the rotor flux (d-q axes).
- Neural Network-based methods require a significant amount of training data and longer signal segments to reliably build the model and successfully differentiate the particular fault classes.
- On the other hand, the proposed Clarke Vector Hodograph method, demonstrates significant advantages over the mentioned methods by successfully using only a single cycle of current signals (in basic configuration) and allows for significantly lower sampling frequencies, thus enabling rapid diagnostics with optimized data acquisition and transmission rates suitable for real-time industrial applications.

In summary, the proposed method provides accurate fault detection and severity classification using very short signal segments recorded at lower sampling frequencies, significantly reducing input data requirements compared to other approaches and eliminating many disadvantages of the aforementioned methods.

The proposed processing method is relatively fast, making it suitable for practical implementations in industrial monitoring systems. When the model is established, testing shows that the median time of the evaluation of a single new incoming sample is at the level of 50 microseconds on the computer equipped with an Intel Core i7-11800H processor using the ellipse fitting variant of parameterization (the recommended one). In practical application, the program would not be implemented in MATLAB, but in a low-level, efficient language such as C. Hence, in terms of computational requirements, the presented method is fully capable of being deployed in practice.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the authors present a simple method for modeling and evaluating the fault of the induction motor stator winding. The method is based on the analysis of geometric features (shape and orientation angle) of Clarke vector hodographs. Two alternative approaches for the estimation of hodogram parameters are proposed; however, in practice, the authors recommend using the ellipse fitting approach, which is more robust. It means that if, by any chance, the segmentation returns a non-perfect data range (not exactly one full loop but a smaller or greater range of samples), the PCA algorithm, which, practically speaking, assesses directional variances, can be thrown off by uneven distribution of samples in α - β space. On the other hand, the ellipse fitting approach analyzes the overall shape of a hodograph, so the sample distribution does not have to be balanced. Using the presented method, only a single period of phase current data is required. For practical application, the model of feature space can be constructed using experimental data registered on a test rig that employs the particular motor, which is entirely feasible for industrial applications. It is important to note that this demonstration presents the model for a single-phase fault. In practice, this has to be replicated for all three phases. Although for all phases, the behavior of the angle and shape coefficient is expected to be similar, the angle will be shifted by approximately 120° per phase. Finally, GMM models for all three phases can be merged into one. It will allow the universal classification of the upcoming data and interpret it properly, regardless of the particular phase being damaged.

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Jacek Wodecki received the Ph.D. in technical diagnostics from the Wrocław University of Science and Technology (WUST), Wrocław, Poland, in 2019. He is currently an Assistant Professor and a member of the Digital Mining Center. His research interests include time-series analysis, stochastic modeling, and statistical analysis of real data with heavy-tailed behavior, machine condition monitoring and fault detection, signal processing, data processing and analysis.

Anna Michalak received the MSc in pure mathematics from the Wrocław University of Science and Technology (WUST), Wrocław, Poland, in 2015. She is currently a member of the Digital Mining Center. Her research interests include time-series analysis, stochastic modeling, and statistical analysis of real data with heavy-tailed behavior (especially data related to the mining industry and financial time series).

Justyna Hebda-Sobkowicz received the Ph.D. in mining and geology from the Wrocław University of Science and Technology (WUST), Wrocław, Poland, in 2023. She is currently an Assistant Professor and a member of the Digital Mining Center. Her research interests include time-series analysis, stochastic modeling, and statistical analysis of real data with heavy-tailed behavior, machine condition monitoring and fault detection, signal processing, data modeling, and analysis.

Radosław Zimroz received the M.Sc. degree in electronics (acoustics/signal processing), the Ph.D. degree in mining engineering (predictive maintenance of mining machines) and the D.Sc. (habilitation, predictive maintenance) degree in mining engineering from Wrocław University of Science and Technology (WUST), Wrocław, Poland, in 1998, 2002, and 2011, respectively. Since 2021, he has been a Full Professor with the WUST, where he is currently the Dean of the Faculty of GeoEngineering Mining and Geology and the leader of Digital Mining Center with strong focus on machine condition and process monitoring, data modeling and analysis, signal processing, fault detection and prognosis, inspection robotics, etc. He has authored and co-authored more than 250 papers in refereed journals and conference presentations (Scopus) with 4k citations. Prof. Zimroz is Vice-President of the Polish Society of Technical Diagnostics.

Agnieszka Wylomańska received the Ph.D. degree in mathematics and the D. Sc. degree in mining and geology from the Wrocław University of Science and Technology (WUST), Wrocław, Poland, in 2006 and 2015, respectively. She is currently a Professor with the Faculty of Pure and Applied Mathematics, WUST, and a member of the Hugo Steinhaus Center for Stochastic Processes. She is the author of more than 150 research papers in the area of applied and industrial mathematics. Her research interests include time-series analysis, stochastic modeling, and statistical analysis of real data with heavy-tailed behavior (especially technical data related to the mining industry, indoor air quality, and financial time series). Prof. Wylomanska is the Editor-in-Chief of *Mathematica Applicanda*.

Marcin Wolkiewicz received the M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees in electrical engineering from Wrocław University of Technology, Wrocław, Poland, in 2007 and 2012, respectively. He is an Assistant Professor with the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Department of Electrical Machines, Drives, and Measurements, Wrocław University of Technology. He has authored/coauthored nearly 35 journal and conference papers. His research interests include fault monitoring and diagnosis of electrical drives using signal analysis, including advanced methods and transforms.

Krzysztof Szabat received the Ph.D. and D.Sc. degrees in automatic control of electrical drives from the Electrical Engineering Faculty, Wrocław University of Technology, Wrocław, Poland, in 2003 and 2008, respectively. Since 1999, he has been a Member of the academic staff with the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Wrocław University of Technology. He is the author and coauthor of over 100 journal and conference papers. His research interests include the application of control theory, artificial intelligence methods, and microprocessor techniques to electrical drive control. Prof. Szabat has been a Reviewer of the IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON INDUSTRIAL ELECTRONICS since 2005.

Sebastien Weisse received an engineering degree from ENSICAEN in 1998. Since 1999, he has worked on various subjects but essentially in the aeronautical domain with more than 20 years of experience, and more than 15 years of experience as a testability/health monitoring expert. Leader of the testability on multiple projects for AIRBUS, BOEING, DASSAULT and other aeronautical top industries during his carrier, he is now in charge of these functions for Safran Electrical & Power: "Support, Maintenance & Services technologies" SAFRAN Roadmap delegate, Member SAFRAN Regulation & Standards Governance (Domain 19: Health Monitoring) and BNAE GT021 (Testability / Health monitoring expert workgroup) delegate.

Jerome Valire received an engineering degree from Polytech Nantes in 2000. Since 2000, he worked on various subjects but essentially in aeronautical domain with more than 20 years of experience, and more than 15 years of experience as system engineer expert, technical leader of different distribution project for Safran like the A350, he is now in charge of the distribution road map for Safran Electrical & Power